

Косицы (свободные концы ленты на бескозырке) [10]. Употребление слова в данном значении не встречается ни в одном словаре. В Морском словаре значение слова указано, как «концы флага в виде прямоугольных треугольников» [15].

Хурда (вещевое имущество) [10]. Слово не упоминается ни в одном словаре. Предположительно, может быть видоизмененным «хурды-мурды», употребляемым в Сибири в значении «домашний скарбишка, всячина, пожитки» [4].

Понятийный мир жизни военного моряка в произведениях В. Пикуля, А. Покровского и Э. Овечкина, в основном, представлен единицами военно-морского жаргона. Очевидно, что большинство слов перешли из общепотребительных в разряд военно-морских жаргонизмов, приобретя специфическое, не свойственное им изначально значение. В то же время можно отметить языковые единицы, которые в первоначальном значении принадлежали к профессионализмам. Следует уточнить, что военно-морской жаргон имеет и локальные особенности, выражающиеся в использовании отдельных языковых единиц только в некоторых экипажах.

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THE MODELING OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY IN THE FIELD OF TOURISM IN THE TEACHING ENVIRONMENT OF A NON-LINGUISTIC UNIVERSITY

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Abstract

The article concerns a concept problem of modeling of foreign language professional activity in the field of tourism in the teaching environment of a non-linguistic university. It is determined by the need to increase the level of foreign language communicative competence of bachelors in the direction of training «Tourism», which can effectively carry out professional activities in the context of intercultural communication. An important component of foreign language communicative competence in the field of professional communication is the knowledge of various types and genres of terminology, the rules for their construction, as well as the ability to create and understand them taking into account the situation of communication.

Keywords: *tourism, model, professionogram, guide, travel guide, excursion, web quest, hypertext, brochure.*

The need to solve the problem of modeling in this study is dictated by the fact [1, p.34-39] that the construction and use of models allows you to quickly respond to external and internal changes in the educational process related to the needs of graduates, the requirements of the labor market, society, the state, changes in standards and norms that the University focuses on in the process of training future personnel for a specific industry, including for the tourism business. The ability to replace elements in the built models allows researchers and practitioners to develop an adaptive learning strategy. Modeling ideas do not contradict the modern competence approach, but they are organically combined with it. In modern pedagogical science, a model approach is widely used, which is expressed in the active use of models in all its branches and stages [2, p.89-94].

We consider the process of modeling in the classical system, taking into account the relationship with the profession and the direction of training "Tourism", which determines the General cultural and professional competence of the graduate.

Modeling is a General scientific method of studying any phenomena, consisting in the construction and study of specific objects, systems - models of other initial objects [3, p.191].

In philosophy, a model is understood as "such a mentally imagined or materially realized system that, by displaying or reproducing the object of research, is able to replace it so that its research gives us new information about this object" [4, p.19]. This definition emphasizes the epistemological role of models.

According to the New dictionary of methodological terms and concepts, the model (from French. *Modèle*, Lat. *Model*-measure, sample) in the broad sense is a simplified mental or symbolic image of an object or system of objects used as their "substitutes" and tools, including training [5, p.448].

The essential features of modeling include the following: the presence of an intermediate object that replaces the original; the intermediary object displays the original, i.e. it has significant similarities with it; the study of the intermediary object allows you to get new information about the original.

Modeling in training has a number of differences from modeling in scientific knowledge, due to the content and method of using models. First, the educational situation is a model, since the tasks used in the educational process are models of tasks that occur in reality. At the same time, the model nature of tasks and situations must be understood not only by the teacher, but also implemented by the students themselves. Secondly, many concepts that students need to learn are based on models, for example, formulas, schemes [6, p.185].

In the methodology of teaching foreign languages, the definition of modeling coincides with the General scientific interpretation, namely, with the method of studying objects of different nature using their analogues (models) to determine or refine the characteristics of existing or newly constructed objects. In foreign language classes, various aspects of educational activity are modeled in order to find the optimal variant of

such activity, as well as the nature of the educational activity of the teacher and students who implement the concept of the chosen method of teaching [5, p.448].

Modeling is widely used in professional training of specialists, including [7, p.232] in foreign-language professional training of N. I. Almazova, M.O. Antyushina, M.B. Ganochevskaya, I. E. Mezhujeva, O.B. Solovyova and O.Y. Levchenko, E. V. Markarian, I. A. Shpachenko indicate the effectiveness of using modeling in foreign language classes for future specialists in the field of Tourism [24, p.148]. The analysis of the literature on this issue shows that the use of modeling has a positive impact on the theoretical and practical training of specialists of various profiles, allows students to reveal the goals of professional training, create conditions for ensuring a high scientific level and creative nature of the educational process, adapt theoretical knowledge to practical professional activities, create motivation for students to self-development.

However, the essence of modeling is understood by researchers in different ways. Modeling is defined as a skill included in the structure of Gnostic skills of students; a General scientific method, the use of which is aimed at the formation of professional and personal qualities of future specialists in the process of studying at University; "[6, p.185] The method of forming the content of training in the form of a set of tasks, tasks and exercises that together fully reflect professional activity from goal setting to self-control and analysis of results, both in the main professional functions and in their elements" [9, p.236].

The use of modeling technology in foreign language classes ensures the creation of conditions under which students have the opportunity to master a foreign language communicative competence at a level that allows them to carry out comprehensive tourist services in accordance with quality standards. This technology helps students get a complete picture of their future profession, as the specialist model acts as a substitute for real professional activity and performs a cognitive function for students. In addition, the expediency of modeling professional activity in the process of teaching a foreign language is due to the fact that, as N. I. Almazova notes, automatism will function freely in the conditions of difficulties in which it was formed [10, p.446]. Modeling of real life situations [7, p.232], including professional life situations, with an emphasis on independent educational activities will serve to create an authentic educational context [5, p.448].

Let's turn to the creation of a model of foreign-language professional activity of personnel in the field of tourism. To do this, first of all, we will analyze the qualification requirements for future employees of the tourism industry.

The study of the tourism Manager's professionogram shows that the dominant activities of this profession are the formation, promotion and implementation of a tourist product, the development of excursion routes. The leading place among the abilities that ensure the success of professional activity is given to communicative abilities: verbal abilities, which imply

the ability to speak clearly, expressively, as well as oratorical abilities, including the ability to correctly express their thoughts, convince [11, p.464].

As you can see, the ability to communicate verbally in a foreign language is very important for tourism workers. This circumstance is due to the fact that, firstly, in the tourism system, the consumers of tourist services may be representatives of a different language culture. Secondly, a graduate of the training direction "Tourism" can get a job abroad in accordance with the obtained qualification.

Analysis of the literature on the theoretical foundations of tourism development, the assessment of the quality of tourist services, the problem of training specialists in the field of tourism allowed us to conclude that the dominant function of tourism workers is information (Galanin Yu.G., 2010; Laikova M. I. (Лайкова М.И.), 2009; O'Shannessy V., 2008).

Mutual understanding with consumers of tourist services belonging to different cultures implies that the staff has cultural knowledge, ability and readiness to understand the mentality of carriers of another culture and their national characteristics, possession of the value system of representatives of another culture and the value system of their own culture [12, p.15]. Due to the fact that English has the status of the language of international communication and is widely used in the field of tourism, including by clients, non-English-speaking cultures, tourism workers, it is important to have the skills to identify cultural values accompanied by tourists and communicate in accordance with the identified values.

Students in the field of training "Tourism" can work as guides. The specifics of the professional activity of tour guides is that their speech is public and takes place in the context of intercultural communication, which imposes on them responsibility for speech behavior. Modeling of various types of excursions in a foreign language lesson should be based on the heterogeneity and variability of tourist groups [13, p.253].

Analysis of foreign literature on the problem of training food industry workers shows that representatives of this industry should be able to describe certain dishes, recommend a choice of dishes in accordance with the preferences of consumers. The description of dishes should be bright due to the use of adjectives, but at the same time concise and natural. Harris notes that a restaurant waiter should use as many senses as possible in communication: sound, appearance, and possibly smell. When describing a dish, the waiter can show it to the customer. If the consumer does not agree with the bill, the waiter can describe how the bill was drawn up [14, p.169].

The next object of professional activity of tourism workers is the tourist information center, whose employees provide free information services to meet the information requests of visitors. In particular, specialists give advice on travel issues through direct contact or telephone conversation, choose an individual tour route, inform about cultural and sports events in the area, attractions, nearby localities, answer questions from tourists, implement recommendations [15, p.146-148].

Thus, we have identified the main communication facilities that meet the real needs of tourism professionals. Travel staff should be prepared to issue statements of various lengths: from short, concise statements from the reception staff of the hotel complex to detailed statements offered by travel agents and information center staff. These statements are not prepared and are subject to processing in accordance with customer requests. Speech works of guides are more prepared, they require mastery of oratory, they are distinguished by imagery, emotionality, visibility, etc. Regardless of the sphere of tourism, a tourism specialist acts as a "cultural intermediary", as an intermediary in the process of cultural exchange between tourists and the host country, and the attitude of guests to this country and its culture will depend on their professionalism [7, p.232].

Implementing certain communicative intentions in situations of professional communication, the bachelor of tourism creates a foreign-language professional terminology in a monological form.

Next, we will go to the description of the model of preparing a bachelor of tourism for foreign-language professional activity, i.e. implementation of the created model of foreign-language professional activity in the educational process. Research of scientific works allows us to conclude that the forms and methods of training that are adequate to professional tasks should be thought out, in particular, modeling of professional activity situations, the use of role-playing and business games [16, p. 99-110].

Let's consider the modeling of foreign-language professional activity in the educational process, which from the point of view of the competence paradigm of activity has a special relevance, since the competence behavior of the subject of activity is manifested in a specific situation [17, p.216].

Based on the provisions of the personal-oriented approach, which declares the absolute value of the individual, the researcher notes that the educational situation should be focused not so much on the acquisition of certain theoretical knowledge and practical skills by students, but on "independent free development of their future profession", activation of "personal-creative, reflexive-value and semantic mechanisms of self-development and professional self-determination", creation of opportunities for taking responsibility for their actions, analysis of their actions. The content of the professional activity situation should include a new type of experience that the future specialist will have to master [18, p.210].

The fact that simulation modeling in the process of teaching a foreign language in higher educational institutions should be aimed at developing the independence of the future specialist is evidenced by the fact that simulation modeling in the process of teaching a foreign language in higher educational institutions should be aimed at developing the independence of the future specialist. In simulated situations, the author writes, it is necessary to provide the future professional with real opportunities to act on their own behalf, to master various strategies and tactics of foreign-language professionally-oriented communication [19, p.24].

Thus, based on the above positions of researchers, we can conclude that the modeling of situations of foreign-language professional communication of tourism workers should be a simplified reproduction in the educational process of situations of professional communication of tourism workers with consumers of tourist services. It is designed to promote the development of students' mobility and readiness for independent implementation of future foreign language communicative professional activities. From the above, it follows that, first, the simulated situations in relation to the tourism industry should include the possibility of creating an oral foreign-language professional terminology by students, during which employees implement certain communicative intentions in accordance with the specifics of the tourism industry. Secondly, in recreated situations in foreign language classes in higher education institutions, it is necessary to equip students with professionally marked strategies [16, p.99-110], which ensure the independent formation of terminology.

The analysis of scientific literature shows that interactive and active methods are widely used in modeling professional activity in the process of higher education. training methods, among which an important place is given to business and role-playing games. "The business game is a reproduction of a typical business situations in game mode, the analysis of the implications of behavior of participants. "The difference between business and role-playing games is that role-playing games do not have a "rigid model" in the form of game rules and approximate structure in the game. The role-playing game offers an uncertain situation, the content of which depends on the participant of the game. As a result, role-playing games require students to have knowledge about the simulated professional activity and social roles [9, p.236].

Thus, in this article, it was revealed that the modeling of professional tourism activities in foreign language classes in a non-linguistic University involves, first, the development of a model of foreign-language professional activity of tourism bachelors, the elements of which we attributed to the communicative intentions implemented by specialists in communicating with consumers of tourist services, typical communicative situations of professional communication, objects of professional activity, professional terminology. Secondly, the choice of forms and methods of training that provide students with imitation of foreign-language professional activities and the acquisition of professional competencies. These include modeling typical communicative situations, organizing and conducting role-playing games, and organizing work with professionally significant texts.

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BASIC PRINCIPLES OF THE COMMUNICATIVE METHOD OF TEACHING THE KAZAKH LANGUAGE

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ҚАЗАҚ ТІЛІН ОҚЫТУДЫҢ КОММУНИКАТИВТІ ӘДІСІНІҢ НЕГІЗГІ ПРИНЦИПТЕРІ

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Abstract

The article discusses the communicative method of teaching, which is a necessary basis for adaptation to the conditions of intercultural communication aimed at the formation of students' communicative competence. We will talk about the basic principles of the communicative method of language learning, the advantages and effectiveness of the communicative method, as well as who benefits from the communicative method of learning, the purpose of the communicative method.

Аннотация

Мақалада студенттердің коммуникативтік құзыреттілігін қалыптастыруға бағытталған мәдениетаралық қарым-қатынас жағдайларына бейімделу үшін қажетті негіз болып табылатын оқытудың коммуникативті әдісі қарастырылған. Тіл үйренудің коммуникативті әдісінің негізгі принциптері, коммуникативті әдістің артықшылықтары мен тиімділігі, оқытудың коммуникативті әдісі кімге пайдалы екендігі және коммуникативті әдістің мақсаты жайлы сөз етіледі.

Keywords: *communicative method, speech skills, lexical fund, grammatical structure, language barrier.*

Кілт сөздер: *коммуникативті әдіс, сөйлеу дағдылары, лексикалық қор, грамматикалық құрылым, тілдік кедергі.*

Жалпы тілдерді оқытудың коммуникативті әдісінің негізгі міндеті – тіл үйренушіге белгілі тілдік кедергіден арылуға көмектесу. Қазақ тілі пәнінің ерекшелігі - практикалық тапсырмалардың негізгі дағдыларын қалыптастыруға бағытталған дәстүрлі әдістермен қатар жаңа білім беру

технологияларын кеңінен қолдану қажеттілігін айқындау. Жалпы өзге тілді үйретуде, оқытуда келесі білім беру технологиялары қолданылады:

- коммуникативтік оқыту технологиясы - студенттердің коммуникативтік құзыреттілігін қалыптастыруға бағытталған;